

INTERIM REPORT

Archaeological Excavations at the Rock of Lough Key

(MacDermot's Rock / Castle Island)

Lough Key, Co. Roscommon, Ireland

Licence No. 19E0348 / Ministerial Consent E00548

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With support from the Royal Irish Academy, Saint Louis University,
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February 2025 (Revised February 2026)

1. Introduction

The Rock of Lough Key, also known as MacDermot’s Rock or Castle Island, is a small island situated several hundred metres from the southern shore of Lough Key in County Roscommon, Ireland. Rising between one and two metres above the modern lake level, the island served as the principal residence of the MacDermot kings of Moylurg from at least the twelfth century through the late sixteenth century, and was subsequently transformed into a Victorian folly by the architect John Nash in the early nineteenth century.

Three seasons of archaeological excavation were carried out on the island in 2019, 2022, and 2023 under licence 19E0348, with subsequent Ministerial Consent granted as E00548. Post-excavation analysis has continued through 2024 and into 2026, supported by grants from the Royal Irish Academy, Saint Louis University, Denison University, and the University of Minnesota Morris. This interim report synthesises the results of excavation, post-excavation analysis, and specialist studies completed to date, and is submitted in fulfilment of requirements for the Royal Irish Academy National Committee on Archaeology and licensing obligations to National Monuments and the National Museum of Ireland.

The project aims to produce a comprehensive final publication by May 2026. This report represents a substantial update on the Summer 2024 interim report, incorporating the refined site phasing completed by Finan and Schryver, the second interim faunal report by Soderberg (May 2025), five radiocarbon dates from the University of Arizona AMS and TIME laboratories, and the results of geological, shoreline, and materials analyses.

2. Excavation Methodology

The excavation was conducted entirely by hand using trowel, shovel, and mattock. Apart from the topsoil contexts, all soil was sieved through quarter-inch mesh to maximise recovery of animal bone and small finds. Context numbering was maintained across all three seasons, with numbers beginning at 1 (2019), 100 (2022), and 200 (2023) to differentiate between seasons while allowing major features to retain their original context numbers when re-exposed.

In 2019, the initial cuttings (A and B) comprised a 5 x 5 m area and an adjacent 4 x 4 m area on the western end of the island. In 2022, these were expanded with Cuttings C, D, and E, designed to assess the extent of structures identified in 2019, explore the relationship between the cashel wall and the extant enclosure wall, and investigate areas of apparent industrial activity identified through geophysical survey. Cutting F (an expansion of Cutting C) and Cutting G were opened in 2023, each approximately 10 x 10 m with stepped profiles to safely achieve excavation depths of up to two metres. Artefacts were numbered according to National Museum of Ireland standards.

Photogrammetric recording was employed throughout, with orthorectified aerial photography and 3D modelling of key features and sections. Harris Matrix software was used to record and analyse stratigraphic relationships across all cuttings and seasons.

3. Site Phasing

Phasing of the site was completed by Thomas Finan and James Schryver in summer 2024. The phasing is based upon stratigraphic relationships, with dating applied from artefacts recovered within particular contexts and from radiocarbon determinations received in 2020, 2023, and January 2026. No evidence of prehistoric settlement or activity has been identified on the island. Six principal phases have been defined. The radiocarbon dating programme has confirmed the stratigraphic sequence, with results summarised in Section 5.2 below.

Phase 1: Entrance Feature

An entrance feature was identified on the western side of the island on the interior of the extant wall in 2019. Initially interpreted as a break in an early medieval cashel wall, subsequent analysis revealed that this feature predates the cashel, with walls misaligned to the known course of the cashel wall. A large stone (C50) was found at the base of this feature, below lake level in 2019, preventing further investigation. The entrance appears to represent the earliest identifiable structural activity on the island, though its function and date remain imprecise.

Phase 2: Large Yellow Limestone Deposit

The entrance feature was filled with large (20–30 cm) rounded limestone boulders of a distinctive yellow colour (C45, C49). Further contexts of similarly sized and coloured boulders (C159, C165, C250, C273) were identified in 2022 and 2023, revealing a single massive deposit that measured upwards of two metres deep in Cuttings C–F. This deposit was intentionally placed on the island. Context 254, a dark silty mud recovered beneath the cashel wall in Cutting F, yielded a silver ring-headed pin suggesting an early medieval date. A pig femur fragment from C254 returned a radiocarbon date of $1,289 \pm 11$ BP (AA116559; 670–774 cal AD at 95.4% confidence), confirming early medieval activity on the island in the seventh to eighth century and providing a critical *terminus post quem* for the construction of the cashel wall. The collagen quality indicators for this sample (atomic C/N ratio of 3.7, nitrogen yield of 10.3%) fall within the accepted range for reliable radiocarbon determinations on bone.

Phase 3: Early Medieval Cashel Wall and 1185 Burning Event

An early medieval cashel wall was identified in Cuttings B, C, F, Dn, and G. The wall is of drystone construction with two coursed faces, measuring 1.7–2.0 m in width and 1.97 m in depth as recorded in Cutting F. The facing stones are typically 20–30 cm wide and 10 cm thick, with no surviving mortar. The internal fill comprises sub-rounded pebbles and soil. The cashel wall

appears to represent a replacement for the Phase 1 entrance feature, following a semicircular course entirely enclosed within the later extant wall.

A layer of burning was identified on and above the cashel in all areas excavated. Pig bone from context C25, a black loose silty layer on top of the cashel wall, returned a date of 887 ± 53 BP (AA113863; 1030–1247 cal AD at 95.4%). This wide range is attributable to the relatively large error margin on this early determination (Order #2895, January 2020), but the date is consistent with the historically attested fire on the island in 1185 CE. A second bone sample from the postholes in compact clay (C274) returned a tighter date of 883 ± 11 BP (AA116557; 1160–1216 cal AD at 95.4%), which is statistically indistinguishable from C25 and narrows the event firmly to the late twelfth to early thirteenth century. These two dates together strongly support the identification of the burning layer with the 1185 conflagration recorded in the Annals of Loch Cé.

Phase 4: High Medieval Settlement (c. 1185–1578)

The high medieval settlement post-dates the extensive burning layer. Three principal features are associated with this phase. Building 1, defined by stone walls (C4) enclosing a compacted clay floor (C5), was constructed directly above the burn layer. The walls comprise large, roughly hewn limestone and sandstone blocks, including pieces of bright yellow sandstone that may have been imported from outside the region. Within the clay floor, a cache of worked antler cores was recovered, representing a complete sequence of antler-working from raw material to prepared comb blanks.

A large entrance feature to the island was identified through excavation in Cuttings C and F. The entrance comprised very large flagstones (C136), some measuring 1.0 x 0.75 m, laid directly upon the cashel wall and burn deposits. Stone walls with inward-facing dressed surfaces flanked this paved surface, leading toward the collapsed section of the extant wall. Context C213 (equivalent to C109 from 2022), a dark silty deposit overlying the flagstones, yielded a dense concentration of animal bone and high-status artefacts including dress pins, combs, gaming pieces, and dice.

Pig bone from context C223, recovered from postholes on the cashel wall, returned a date of 851 ± 11 BP (AA116558; 1170–1224 cal AD at 95.4%). This date is slightly later than C274 and C25, consistent with post-fire reconstruction activity on the cashel. An area of industrial activity was identified in Cuttings D and G, with extensive deposits of multi-coloured ash, evidence of fine metalworking (green-tinged deposits), and a possible furnace (C256) associated with large flat stones that may have served as anvils. An arc of closely spaced postholes (C274–C275) set in compact clay and ash was identified on the final day of excavation in Cutting F, suggesting a timber structure potentially contemporary with or predating the stone buildings.

Phase 5: Tower House Insertion and Embankment (c. 1441–1578)

Historical sources record that Brian MacDermot constructed a “great regal house” on the island by 1578, at which major feasts were held, including a famous feast for all the bardic poets of Ireland. Architectural analysis by O’Conor et al. (2008) identified the square walls within the later Nash construction as the original tower house, supported by the presence of an arrow slit and a medieval punch-dressed window.

The construction of the tower house involved the addition of substantial quantities of redeposited soil to the eastern portion of the island, retained by a stone batter wall of unmortared large thin stones set at an angle. This effectively enlarged the island’s footprint to accommodate the new structure. A pig bone from context C300, the embankment deposit, returned a radiocarbon date of 412 ± 17 BP (AZT65106; 1441–1491 cal CE at 95.4%). This date is significant: it places the embankment construction in the mid-fifteenth century, nearly a century before the documented tower house construction of c. 1578. This suggests that the process of enlarging the island may have begun considerably earlier than the construction of the tower house itself, perhaps as part of a broader programme of site enhancement by the MacDermot lords. A notable artefact hiatus from the sixteenth to the nineteenth century corresponds to this phase.

Phase 6: Victorian Occupation (c. 1810–present)

Following the award of the Rockingham Estate to Sir John King in 1603, the island appears to have fallen into disuse until approximately 1810, when the architect John Nash designed a folly centred on the MacDermot tower house as part of the development of Rockingham House. Nash added two wings of stone and brick with neo-gothic windows, covered the structure with a concrete facing, and added crenellations to both the tower and the extant enclosure wall. A substantial kitchen with large brick-lined ovens was constructed against the exterior of the northern enclosure wall, with direct lake access via a window. An underwater survey by Niall Brady in 2008 identified a massive midden deposit immediately outside this kitchen.

The Victorian-era modifications included the addition of mortar to the extant wall, which has since dissolved, causing considerable structural deterioration. The artefact assemblage from this phase includes ceramic pipes concentrated near the kitchen entrance, champagne bottle fragments, jam jars, a sardine tin key, and a servant’s button displaying the King family crest.

4. Faunal Assemblage Analysis

Dr John Soderberg (Denison University) has conducted zooarchaeological analysis of the faunal assemblage in sessions spanning July 2021, July 2022, January 2024, and June 2024. His second interim report (May 2025) presents data from the entire 2019 assemblage and approximately half of the 2022 assemblage, comprising over 13,000 identified fragments from 21 contexts. The remaining 2023 material, which represents the largest portion of the assemblage, is yet to be analysed. Nine contexts yielding more than 500 identifiable fragments form the basis of the current analysis. Contexts are organised into four chronological phases: early medieval (pre-twelfth century), high medieval (twelfth to thirteenth century), late medieval (fourteenth to fifteenth century), and post-medieval.

4.1 Taphonomy and Preservation

The assemblage displays generally good preservation, though a significant minority of specimens exhibit staining, accretions, and surface degradation consistent with different taphonomic histories. These variations are primarily attributable to heat damage, supporting the stratigraphic evidence for burning episodes. Fragmentation rates are highest in context C11, a layer containing burned material, indicating intensive processing of carcass remains in this context.

Carnivore gnawing is negligible across all contexts, with fewer than one percent of specimens showing such modification in any given assemblage. This exceptionally low figure suggests that bone refuse was rapidly buried or otherwise protected from scavengers, consistent with the island setting where canid access would have been restricted. Cutmarks are similarly rare but consistent across contexts, ranging from 0.54% to 1.6% of specimens. The low cutmark frequency does not indicate minimal butchery but rather reflects systematic processing with careful disarticulation at joints, where marks are less likely to be inflicted on bone surfaces. Evidence of heat damage varies considerably between contexts but is most prevalent in those associated with the burning event of Phase 3.

4.2 Species Composition

The species ratio is remarkably consistent across all non-modern contexts. The three principal domesticates — cattle, pig, and sheep/goat — dominate the assemblage, with minimal contributions from wild species, birds, fish, and microfauna (the latter categories excluded from the current analysis). The most striking feature of the assemblage is the unusually high proportion of pig relative to cattle. On typical medieval Irish rural sites, cattle overwhelmingly dominate the faunal record. At the Rock of Lough Key, pig representation approaches or exceeds that of cattle in several contexts. This elevated proportion of pig aligns with patterns observed at medieval castle sites across Ireland and Britain and is strongly suggestive of feasting activities. The historical record explicitly associates the Rock of Lough Key with large-scale feasting, most notably the feast organised by Brian MacDermot in 1578 for the bardic poets of Ireland.

Sheep and goat are present in lower numbers across all phases. Identification to species within the sheep/goat category is hampered by the fragmented nature of many postcranial elements, though only a single goat horn core has been positively identified. The sheep/goat assemblage comprises primarily mature individuals, suggesting exploitation for secondary products (wool, milk) rather than slaughter for meat.

4.3 Cattle

Cattle remain the most abundant species overall, with a broad representation of skeletal parts across all contexts. Analysis using NISP (Number of Identified Specimens), MNE (Minimum Number of Elements), and MAU (Minimum Animal Units) reveals subtle but interpretively significant differences in element frequency. A consistent negative relationship between food utility indices and element frequency indicates that high-utility elements — those bearing the greatest meat mass — were more intensively fragmented than low-utility elements. This pattern is diagnostic of systematic marrow extraction and intensive carcass processing.

A notable feature of the cattle assemblage is the presence of unusually large proximal humeri. These specimens are metrically distinct from the remainder of the cattle postcranial material and may represent either unusually large individuals or, more likely, selective deposition of prestigious cuts. Large humeri bearing substantial meat masses are well attested in the Irish historical literature as prestige portions associated with feasting, where specific joints were allocated according to social rank. The cattle metrical data indicates a predominantly female herd, consistent with dairy-oriented husbandry, though the presence of some larger individuals may indicate bulls or oxen.

4.4 Pig

The pig assemblage provides some of the most compelling evidence for feasting at the Rock. Analysis of 47 mandibles using standard tooth wear stages reveals a strongly patterned age-at-death profile. The overwhelming majority of pigs were slaughtered in their first or second year, with a pronounced concentration at the one-to-two year age class. This kill-off pattern is consistent with provisioning for consumption rather than maintenance of a breeding herd, and points to the systematic rearing or procurement of young pigs specifically for large-scale meat production.

Several pig specimens exhibit severe dental pathologies. Two mandibles in particular (C112_781 and C112_746) display abnormal tooth development and enamel hypoplasia that may indicate metabolic stress consistent with confinement or high-density housing conditions. These pathologies, if confirmed through further analysis, would suggest that pigs were being kept in restricted spaces on or near the island, potentially in pens or enclosures where overcrowding led to nutritional and developmental deficiencies. Such a management regime would be entirely consistent with the provisioning of a high-status settlement engaged in periodic large-scale feasting.

4.5 Chronological Patterns and Integration with Phasing

The phasing completed by Finan and Schryver in 2024 enabled Soderberg to aggregate faunal material from equivalent contexts across seasons and cuttings. This process was substantively confirmed by the nature of the faunal material itself: comparable contexts across different excavation areas yielded internally consistent taphonomic signatures, species ratios, and fragmentation patterns. This correspondence between stratigraphic interpretation and zooarchaeological evidence represents a powerful independent validation of the site phasing.

The radiocarbon dates now available provide chronological anchors for the faunal sequence. The C254 date (670–774 cal AD) demonstrates that animal bone deposition on the island began in the early medieval period, predating the cashel wall. The cluster of dates from C25, C274, and C223 (collectively spanning 1160–1224 cal AD) places the densest occupation deposits firmly in the high medieval period, while the C300 embankment date (1441–1491 cal CE) confirms late medieval activity. The faunal assemblage as a whole is argued to represent a unique and unparalleled window into the animal economy and feasting practices of a Gaelic lordly settlement, the full significance of which will be assessed upon completion of the entire assemblage analysis including the substantial 2023 material.

5. Specialist Studies and Scientific Analyses

5.1 Geological Survey

A geological survey of the stone on the island was completed by Ronan McCool in late 2023, with a report submitted in early 2024. Twenty samples were examined, of which nine showed evidence of water erosion consistent with lakeshore collection. Four main geological units were identified from the samples, cross-referenced against the Geological Survey of Ireland published maps and verified through visits to three shore locations. The survey concluded that the building stone was collected from different locations along the lakeshore, with the particular source depending on which farmer was tasked with the work and prevailing wind conditions. The presence of yellow sandstone not native to the north Roscommon area confirms some importation of building materials.

5.2 Radiocarbon Dating Programme

Five radiocarbon dates have been received from the University of Arizona AMS Laboratory (Orders #2895 and #4062) and TIME Laboratory (Order #4351). All dates were processed using the OxCal calibration programme (versions 4.3 and 4.4) against the IntCal13 and IntCal20 atmospheric datasets. The results are presented in Table 1 below.

Table 1. Radiocarbon dates from the Rock of Lough Key (19E0348)

Context	Lab No.	Material	¹⁴ C Age BP	Cal AD (95%)	Phase Association
C254	AA116559	Bone (pig)	1,289 ± 11	670–774	Phase 2: Pre-cashel deposit
C25	AA113863	Bone (pig)	887 ± 53	1030–1247	Phase 3: Burn layer on cashel
C274	AA116557	Bone (pig)	883 ± 11	1160–1216	Phase 4: Postholes in clay
C223	AA116558	Bone (pig)	851 ± 11	1170–1224	Phase 4: Postholes on cashel
C300	AZT65106	Bone (pig)	412 ± 17	1441–1491	Phase 5: Embankment

The five dates confirm the stratigraphic phasing in all respects. The earliest date, from C254, establishes activity on the island in the seventh to eighth century, consistent with the typological dating of the silver ring-headed pin from the same context and providing a robust terminus post quem for the cashel wall construction. The three dates from C25, C274, and C223 cluster tightly in the late twelfth to early thirteenth century, confirming the association of the burning event with the 1185 fire and the subsequent high medieval settlement phase. The statistical overlap between C25 (887 ± 53 BP) and C274 (883 ± 11 BP) is notable; the latter's tighter error margin reflects improved measurement precision in the more recent analysis. The C223 date (851 ± 11 BP) is marginally later, consistent with post-fire reconstruction activity.

The most recently received date, from C300 (412 ± 17 BP; 1441–1491 cal CE), provides the first absolute date for the embankment construction on the eastern portion of the island. This mid-fifteenth-century date predates the documented construction of the MacDermot tower house by approximately a century, suggesting that the process of island enlargement began before the tower house was erected. Three further samples submitted to the University of Arizona (C49, C150, C159) are awaited and will provide additional chronological control for Phases 2 and 3.

5.3 Shoreline and Landscape Surveys

A survey of the shore of Lough Key south of Castle Island identified quarrying locations that supplied stone to the island. Aerial photographs and video were collected for documentation. Additional survey along the northern shore of the Rock identified stone features interpreted as boat slips, a winding causeway to the mainland (first observed in aerial photographs in 2019), and what appears to be a human-made landing area. An underwater survey by Niall Brady in 2008 had previously suggested a number of submerged features associated with the island, including the midden deposit outside the Victorian kitchen.

5.4 XRF and Materials Analysis

X-ray fluorescence (XRF) analysis is being applied to multiple material types from the excavation. The primary focus to date has been the characterisation of mortar samples from the extant enclosure wall and Victorian-era modifications. Portable XRF provides rapid, non-destructive elemental profiling that enables the differentiation of construction phases through compositional signatures in binder and aggregate chemistry.

The analytical approach exploits differences in major element concentrations (CaO , SiO_2 , Al_2O_3) to distinguish between binder-rich lime mortars and aggregate-dominated compositions, and uses trace element ratios (Sr, Rb, Mn, Fe) to identify distinct raw material sources and refine typological groupings. Multivariate statistical techniques, including Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and hierarchical clustering, are being applied to the elemental dataset to objectively group samples by composition and correlate compositional clusters with construction phases identified through excavation.

Preliminary results indicate clear compositional differences between the original medieval mortar associated with the cashel and enclosure wall, and the Victorian repair mortar added by Nash or the King family in the early nineteenth century. The Victorian mortar, which was applied in an attempt to prevent further deterioration of the extant wall, has since dissolved and caused considerable damage where applied. This dissolution pattern is itself informative, suggesting that the Victorian mortar was compositionally incompatible with the original construction — likely a harder Portland-type cement applied to a softer aerial lime substrate. The elemental ratios track this technological change, with the Victorian additions showing characteristically different CaO/SiO_2 ratios and trace element profiles compared to the medieval material.

XRF analysis of pottery sherds and other materials from the excavation is ongoing. The integration of XRF data with the stratigraphic and radiocarbon evidence will contribute to a comprehensive understanding of construction chronology and material sourcing at the Rock of Lough Key.

6. Artefact Assemblage

The artefact assemblage spans the full occupation sequence of the island, with the majority of diagnostic finds dating to the high medieval period. The assemblage includes metalwork (silver pins, bronze needle, iron nails, buckles, and hooks), ceramics (green-glazed medieval pottery, Victorian transferware, and ceramic pipe stems), glass (window glass, a broken glass bead, blue glass fragment), worked bone and antler (a bone pin, worked antler cores representing comb production), stone (worked flint, possible quern fragments), and shell.

Of particular note is the silver pin with cubic head and decorations down the shaft (C32:1), recovered from a high medieval context, and the silver ring-headed pin from C254 beneath the cashel wall — now securely dated to the seventh to eighth century by the associated radiocarbon determination. A silver penny with long cross (C3:2) provides a numismatic dating point for the medieval occupation. The worked antler cache from the clay floor of Building 1 is significant as evidence of on-site craft production. The Victorian assemblage, including a servant's button with the King family crest, provides direct evidence linking the site to the Rockingham Estate.

All 2019 artefacts have been conserved and are now held at the National Museum of Ireland repository. Artefact data continues to be maintained and updated in accordance with NMI standards.

7. Conservation Concerns

The structural integrity of the ruins on the Rock of Lough Key is a matter of ongoing concern. A northerly storm in the winter of 2020 caused the collapse of the extant wall on the western side of the island, including a toilet tower and associated Victorian crenellations. The collapse exposed rubble consistent with Victorian modifications, but also revealed earlier medieval features including a plinth at the base of the wall. More critically, the standing wall adjacent to the collapse displays a fracture three to four centimetres wide and offset from the wall face. Excavation in 2022 demonstrated that this section of wall lacks significant structural support, with Victorian-era mortar having largely dissolved. The project team considers this area to be at imminent risk of further collapse and recommends urgent stabilisation.

The Nash additions to the tower house are similarly precarious, with whole segments breaking away from the core medieval structure. The concrete facing applied during the Victorian period continues to deteriorate, and the interfaces between the wings and the tower house are progressively weakening. The XRF analysis of the Victorian mortar (Section 5.4) has confirmed the compositional incompatibility between the repair mortar and the original wall fabric, providing a scientific basis for understanding the ongoing deterioration.

8. Conclusions and Future Work

The excavations at the Rock of Lough Key have revealed a complex, multi-period site of national significance. The radiocarbon dating programme has provided five absolute dates that confirm the stratigraphic phasing in all respects, establishing a chronological framework spanning from early medieval activity in the seventh to eighth century (C254: 670–774 cal AD), through the high medieval burning event and settlement (C25, C274, C223: collectively 1160–1224 cal AD), to late medieval island enlargement in the mid-fifteenth century (C300: 1441–1491 cal CE).

The faunal assemblage is of exceptional importance, providing what may be an unparalleled view into the animal economy and feasting practices of a Gaelic lordly settlement. The unusually high proportion of pig, the evidence for intensive carcass processing, the strongly patterned age-at-death profiles, and the association with historically attested feasting events make this assemblage uniquely significant for understanding medieval Irish society. The dental pathologies observed in pig specimens raise the possibility of on-site animal management under confined conditions, a hypothesis that will be further tested through isotope analysis.

Outstanding work includes the completion of Soderberg’s analysis of the 2023 faunal material (representing the largest portion of the assemblage), the receipt and integration of three further radiocarbon dates (C49, C150, C159), ongoing XRF and materials analyses, a study of the ceramic pipe assemblage, and the production of final publication-quality illustrations and plans. Isotope analysis of cattle, pig, and sheep/goat remains is planned to investigate provisioning networks and animal mobility, which will further illuminate the economic and social dimensions of feasting at the Rock.

The project remains on track for submission of a final monograph by May 2026.